

A co-evolutionary approach to interpretable reinforcement learning in environments with continuous action spaces - Supplementary material

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Fig. 1. Plot in score-complexity of the best agent obtained (w.r.t. score) in the MountainCarContinuous-v0 environment compared to the solutions find in either the literature or the OpenAI Gym’s leaderboard for which the \mathcal{M} metric can be computed. Liventsev et al. refers to the results presented in [1]. Oller et al. refers to the results shown in [2].

Fig. 2. Plot in score-complexity of the best agent obtained (w.r.t. score) in the LunarLanderContinuous-v2 environment compared to the solutions find in either the literature or the OpenAI Gym's leaderboard for which the \mathcal{M} metric can be computed. Goecks et al. refers to the results presented in [3].

Fig. 3. Evolution of the actions through the evolutionary process in the MountainCarContinuous-v0 environment. The blue line represents the mean of all the individuals, while the shaded area represents the standard deviation.

Fig. 4. Evolution of the actions through the evolutionary process in the LunarLanderContinuous-v2 environment. The blue line represents the mean of all the individuals, while the shaded area represents the standard deviation.